

A double numerical perspective of the viscous Rayleigh-Taylor instability in a horizontally confined flow

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In this article, the classical Rayleigh-Taylor instability is extended to situations where the fluid is completely confined, in both the vertical and horizontal directions. This article starts with the two-dimensional (2D) viscous periodic case with finite height where the effect of adding surface tension to the interface is analyzed. This problem is simulated from a dual perspective: first, the linear stability analysis obtained when the Navier-Stokes equations are linearized and regularized in terms of density and viscosity; and second, looking at the weakly compressible version of a multiphase smoothed particle hydrodynamics (WCSPH) method. The evolution and growth rates of the different fluid variables during the linear regime of the SPH simulation are compared to the computation of the eigenvalues and eigenfunctions of the viscous version of the Rayleigh-Taylor stability (VRTI) analysis with and without surface tension. The classical horizontally periodic (VRTI) case is now adapted to the case where two additional left and right walls are included in the problem, representing the cases where a two-phase flow is confined in an accelerated tank. The agreement with the linear stability analysis obtained by a Lagrangian method such as multiphase WCSPH is remarkable.

INTRODUCTION

In many aircraft models, the fuel is transported inside tanks placed along the wing structures. Due to the great extreme accelerations on the aircraft wings, violent fluid movement and strong impacts with the tank walls are produced. This complex fluid phenomenon is known as sloshing. In the analysis of vertically excited sloshing cases, violent sloshing is of great interest for aeroplane manufacturers, where very interesting hydrodynamic phenomena are found, such as the free surface instabilities that appear at the first stages of the movement. These instabilities are an extended version of Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities, where fluid properties such as viscosity and surface tension play a role. An original extension of the RTI appears in the sloshing phenomena when two different fluids are confined in an accelerated tank. In this case, the light fluid overlies a heavier fluid when gravity is present, but the RTI appears when a larger acceleration than gravity is applied to both fluids in the opposite direction to the force of gravity. As explained before, the density gradient is opposed to the difference between the inertial force and gravity.

However, to the best of our knowledge no numerical study on the eigenvalue problem associated to the VRTI in a confined tank has been performed. Therefore, we need to carry out this research study in the case of two-dimensional (2D) geometries where the no-slip boundary conditions are imposed on the top and bottom walls, but also on the lateral walls.

LINEAR STABILITY ANALYSIS

The strategies to perform the linear stability analysis are presented in this section. To study the viscous version of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability, we assume a zero velocity base-flow and regularized density and viscosity distributions that represent two fluids separated

by a common interface. We analyze the evolution of the perturbations by the assumed base-flow. In particular, we are interested in the development of two-dimensional flow structures and the growth rates of the different unstable modes. The calculations have been performed in a 2D computational domain.

Therefore, in order to describe the Rayleigh-Taylor (RT) instability of sharp interface, it seems more consistent to attempt to solve the problem for a transition layer of finite thickness, and then take the limit when the thickness tends to zero. Similarly to the implementation used in [1], we adopt the density and viscosity profiles

$$\bar{\rho} = 1 + A_\rho \tanh(y/L_s) \quad \mu = 1 + A_\mu \tanh(y/L_s) \quad (1)$$

where L_s is the gradient scale length of the density and viscosity layers and A_ρ, A_μ the Atwood numbers associated to density and viscosity.

In the classical 1D instability analysis of the VRTI, a periodic solution with unlimited wavelength in both the horizontal x and spanwise z directions [2] is assumed. In the periodic boundary case, see the top part of Figure 1, the BiGlobal EVP has been solved without the explicit assumption of the periodic structure in the horizontal x direction, but with limited wavelength for the computed eigenvectors in the horizontal direction $k_x > \frac{\pi}{L}$ and infinite spanwise length. The horizontally confined case studied here, see the bottom part of Figure 1, no periodicity assumption is possible, and the 2D formulation is compulsory. The final perturbation equations, see details and nomenclature in [5].

FIG. 1. Schemes of the computational geometry used for the Rayleigh-Taylor simulations. A dashed line at $y = 0$ indicates the interface between fluids. The boundary conditions are: periodic (a) and no-slip (b).

MULTIPHASE SPH FORMULATION

One of the objectives of this work is to prove that the SPH formulation is a valid tool to perform a stability analysis of the VRTI. For that purpose, we are going to discretize the Navier-Stokes equations using the multiphase δ -WCSPH formulation detailed in [3].

In Figure 2, the amplitude perturbations corresponding to the eigenvalue are represented for all the fluid variables for an interface scale length $L_s = 0.01$. The horizontal periodicity of the structure is clearly observable. The wavenumber is obtained after measuring the wavelength of the structure $\lambda_x = 2$ in the picture, and then computing the wavenumber as $k = 2\pi/\lambda_x = \pi$.

In the bottom Figure 2 a snapshot of the evolution of the velocity fields is shown at time $t/t_0 = 5$, when the

FIG. 2. Perturbation amplitudes for the case $k = \pi$, $2H = 2$, $2L = 8$ and $A_\mu = A_\rho = 0.2$ and $S = 0.003$: horizontal velocity (a) and vertical velocity (b). Snapshots of the SPH simulation at $t/t_0 = 5$: the vertical velocity (c) and horizontal velocity (d).

initial flow is excited with $k = \pi$ and both Atwood num-

bers are equal $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.6$. At this time step, the velocity field is immersed in the linear regime after the initial oscillations caused by the combination of the particle setup and the weakly compressible assumption. It is worth noting that the velocity perturbations corresponding to the most unstable mode obtained after the linear stability analysis, see top part of Figure 2, matching well with the velocity snapshots of the SPH simulation.

CONCLUSIONS

The most important conclusions obtained in this work are the following:

- The RTI instability has been numerically studied in 2D with regularized density and viscosity. The model introduces the possibility of confining the fluid either in the vertical or horizontal directions, adding viscosity to both phases and introducing surface tension to the interface.
- The classical 1D formulation is limited to those cases where the horizontal coordinate is periodic, in contrast with the 2D formulation assumed here, which permits studying more general cases, as for example those cases where the fluids are confined and no-slip boundary conditions are necessary for the lateral walls.
- The VRTI instability has been also been simulated with multiphase WCSPH. This method is clearly non-linear but is able to capture the linear regime that is present at the first stage of the simulation. The matching between both formulations is very good in a relevant range of wavenumbers.

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